

FULL PAPER

Title: Co-operative Federalism for Transformation

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Abstract: India is definitely at the crossroads of history in the early 21st century. Not only India is posed to be the 5th largest economy in the world surpassing France, India is one of the few nations which does have nuclear power, India is the fastest growing economy in the world and being largest and stable democracy having rightfully earned reputation of peacekeeper, India also is a rightful claimant of extended UNSC. To bolster India's strength further, more than 50 percent of Indians are below 25 years and more than 65 percent of Indians are below age of 35 years.⁽¹⁾ India being at such an important juncture has all the more responsibility to harness its demographic dividend to be the great nation it is destined to be.

At a juncture as this Co-operative federalism becomes all the more important. The author of this paper tries to analyze the factors which gave rise to active federalism in India and the policy measures which are required to ensure sustainable economic growth and development of all the three tiers of Government. This has been analyzed in the light of the need for fiscal devolution to ensure co-operative federalism thus enabling transformation of India to a responsible emerging global power. To ensure this Co-operative federalism must be fuelled by Fiscal federalism

Keywords: Federalism, Co-operative, Quasi federalism, Fiscal federalism, measures, improve, devolution

Introduction: India is a sovereign socialistic secular democratic republic. The term 'federation' is nowhere used in Indian constitution, India never the less does embody the spirit of Quasi federalism if not Pure federalism.

Even before independence, founding fathers of our nation gave emphasis on autonomy of provinces, since they realized that although they were fighting for a united nation, the nation itself was very large and inherently was a very diverse nation. Due to geographical diversity, linguistic diversity, religious diversity, to have regional diversity in the form varied cultural and traditional thinking was nothing but norm. This had to result in pure federalism. However, at the time of independence, the circumstances which led to freedom of India and the way in which the rest of India was united, necessitated strong central government and thus Constitution itself made India to be 'Indestructible Union of Destructible States'⁽²⁾. The imbalance in power did not cause much rift initially as the political party in power in both centre and states was by and large one. However with emerging regional aspirations which did take the form of regional political parties not only heralded the era of coalition governments at the centre but also necessitated a relook at federalism.

With the emergence of regional political parties, the states came to prominence. It was understood in a better manner that the people of the state were in a better position to

understand the problems of the state as opposed to the Center’s “One Size fits all approach”. With increasing realization of the same the fiscal devolution from center to state via Finance Commission increased gradually increased the states’s share in central tax pool from time to time, for instance, 14th Finance Commission increased state’s share increased from 32% to 42% which is highest and moreover such a devolution is untied and the state can spend the same as it wishes.

However the true test of the democracy lies in the fact that it must ensure participation of the people and accountability from the leaders ⁽⁴⁾. Now this was still not achieved as local governing bodies were still not empowered. Although urban local government originated and developed during British rule itself⁽³⁾, they lacked constitutional recognition and moreover even after independence although the importance of local government was recognised by the founding fathers⁽ⁱ⁾ of our nation, giving or not giving autonomy to local governments was left to the states. Finally 73rd and 74th amendment passed by the Narasimha Rao Government came into effect in 1993 empowering the Local governments at both the urban and rural level. This led to the three tier Government that we have come to be familiar with as of now.

Observations and Discussion

Now, further in the paper the author shall discuss the observations in the problems faced by the state level and local level governments in detail.

State level Government issues

1.Increasing Disparities

After the reforms (new economic reforms with respect to liberalization, privatization and globalization implemented during 1990s), it has been observed that the richer states, with exception of Punjab and Haryana have seen better growth than the poorer states.⁽⁵⁾ The growing disparities is shown in the figure 1.

(i)The independence of India should mean the independence of the whole of India...Independence must begin at the bottom. Thus every village will be a republic... It follows therefore that every village has to be self-sustained and capable of managing its affairs. In this structure composed of innumerable villages, there will be ever widening, ever-ascending circles. Life will be a pyramid with the apex sustained by the bottom - Mahatma Gandhi

2. Use of 2011 census by Finance commission and its impact there of on devolution of Receipts of states

Finance Commission, using 2011 population for devolution of funds has negatively affected those states which have made efforts to control population with regards to fiscal devolution⁽⁶⁾ as has been shown in figure 2. ⁽ⁱⁱ⁾

Note: Calculations do not take into account any adjustments to be made in 2018-19 for the previous financial years. Delhi has not been taken into consideration as it does not have any share in the net proceeds of taxes devolved to states.

Sources: Union Budget Documents; State Budget Documents; Census 2011; Report of the 14th Finance Commission; PRS.

The receipts of some states see comparatively higher change as compared to the others. While Tamil Nadu, Kerala, and Andhra Pradesh see a decrease in their receipts, those of Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan, and Bihar will increase. This increase as a percentage of 2018-19 estimated revenue would have been 0.5% for Uttar Pradesh (Rs 1,810 crore), 0.9% for Rajasthan (Rs 1,364 crore), and 0.8% for Bihar (Rs 1,329 crore). The decreased receipts would have reduced the revenue by 1.2% for Tamil Nadu (Rs 2,051 crore), 1.5% for Kerala (Rs 1,513 crore), and 0.8% for Andhra Pradesh (Rs 1,276 crore).⁽⁰⁷⁾

With the 15th Finance Commission's mandate to use the population data of 2011 for its recommendations, the share of individual states in the union pool of taxes could see changes similar to the changes calculated for 2018-19 (Figure 5). This could reduce the share of some states which have made efforts for population control, and as a result, the proportion of their population in the total population has reduced since 1971. Thus, such states, e.g. Tamil Nadu, Kerala, and Andhra Pradesh, could witness a comparative reduction in their devolution receipts on similar lines. However, note that, in this analysis, we have not factored in any mitigating factor, such as the performance-based incentives that can be proposed by the 15th Finance Commission to reward such states for population control. Such incentives could mitigate the reduction in devolution to these states because of use of the population data of 2011 (instead of the 1971 population data), as illustrated above.⁽⁰⁸⁾

3. Shortfall in GST and the adverse impact of including petrol and crude oil in gst for some states

States have been losing revenue on account of implementation of GST as has been shown in the following table 1⁽⁰⁹⁾:

Table 1: GST compensation grants expected by states in 2018-19

State	Compensation (in Rs crore)	Compensation as percentage of revenue
Andhra Pradesh	2,000	1.3 %
Assam	1,000	1.4 %
Bihar	3,698	2.3 %
Gujarat	10,296	7.3 %
Jammu and Kashmir	3,175	4.9 %
Karnataka	10,800	6.5 %
Madhya Pradesh	2,600	1.7 %
Odisha	4,074	4.1 %
Rajasthan	4,500	3.0 %
Sikkim	111	1.8 %
Tamil Nadu	1,698	1.0 %
Telangana	1,500	1.2 %
Tripura	147	1.0 %
Uttar Pradesh	5,942	1.7 %
West Bengal	9,876	6.7 %

Sources: State Budget Documents; PRS.

Moreover states have been still imposing VAT on petrol and Diesel. There has been more than 20% for 25 of 27 states. This has been illustrated in Figure 3

Figure 3: Effective sales tax/VAT rates levied by states on petrol and diesel (as on November 1, 2018)

Note: The rates shown for Maharashtra are averages of the rates levied in Mumbai-Thane region and the rest of the state.

Sources: Petroleum Planning and Analysis Cell, Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas; PRS.

If according to the structure at hand petrol and diesel are brought into the fold of GST, then even if it is brought under the highest tax slab which is 28%, with no additional levies then CGST and SGST will be levied at 14% each with additional levies, this will result in loss for states because as of now, 25 OF 27 states are levying VAT in excess of 20%.

A case in point is Maharashtra which does levy a tax of 36% shall face an effective loss of 12% , the same is the case with respect to diesel where in the states would lose an estimated 5 to 11% on implementation of GST.

4.Play of Vertical and horizontal imbalances:

Unlike in USA and Canada, where in both states and centre levy tax, in India only the centre has exclusive powers to levy tax which at any rate in is shared with the states. Recently the finance commission has increased the shareable percentage from 32% to 42% which does give the states more unconditional funds to spend on.

In 2010-11 Share of centre was 64.68% in receipts, after transfer the share of centre was 40.20% and state was 59.80%. The same trend intensified gradually as can be seen that in 2016-17 Centre's share after transfer was 33.37%and state was 66.63%. ⁽¹⁰⁾

However even relatively richer states do feel 'cheated' as because of overuse of equity criterion because even the large states do have their own problems as such.

Local Government Issues

In India the local governments are broadly of two types that is urban and rural. Although we did have local governments and even the founding fathers of the nation had realized the importance of the same, the local governments were not empowered.

However, the true essence of democracy lies in the fact that the leaders are accountable and the people are active participants in the process that is democracy. To ensure this in letter and spirit local governments had to be empowered and the very same was achieved through 73rd and 74th amendment.

However despite, having implemented the same, there have been opportunities and challenges. Both of which the author shall be discussing in the following sections.

Rural Local Government

In India, the level of urbanisation has increased from 27.81% in 2001 census to 31.16 % in 2011 census; correspondingly the level of ruralisation has decreased from 72.19% in 2001 census to 69.84% in 2011 census. At any rate one has to realize the fact that, when Mahatma Gandhi told India lives in villages he was absolutely right, and when the same statement is said now, it is not far from the truth.

In such a juncture, it becomes all the more important, to empower the villages through empowering the local bodies financially so that the local government and the people therein play an active role in transforming rural Bharath to shining India in a sustainable and exemplary manner.

The essence behind implementation of the amendments was as follows:

It was meant to provide constitutional sanction to establish "democracy at the grassroots level as it is at the state level or national level". Its main features are as follows: ⁽¹⁰⁾

- The Gram Sabha or village assembly as a deliberative body to decentralised governance has been envisaged as the foundation of the Panchayati Raj System. 73rd Amendment of the Constitution empowered the Gram Sabhas to conduct social audits in addition to its other functions.
- A uniform three-tier structure of panchayats at village (Gram Panchayat — GP), intermediate or block (Panchayat Samiti — PS) and district (Zilla Parishad — ZP) levels.
- All the seats in a panchayat at every level are to be filled by elections from respective territorial constituencies.
- Not less than one-third of the total seats for membership as well as office of chairpersons of each tier have to be reserved for women.
- Reservation for weaker castes and tribes (SCs and STs) have to be provided at all levels in proportion to their population in the panchayats.
- To supervise, direct and control the regular and smooth elections to panchayats, a State Election Commission has The Act has ensured constitution of a State Finance Commission in every State/UT, for every five years, to suggest measures to strengthen finances of Panchayati Raj Institutions.
- To promote bottom-up-planning, the District Planning Committee (DPC) in every district has been accorded to constitutional status.
- An indicative list of 29 items has been given in Eleventh Schedule of the Constitution. Panchayats are expected to play an effective role in planning and implementation of works related to these 29 items.

From the above objectives behind establishing the local government we can see that the primary goal behind establishing the same has been to ensure that the people at grass root level are empowered and the leaders leading the people are made accountable to the people and the people choose their own path of development as such.

The same has no doubt resulted in wonderful success stories as well which are as follows:

Within the core of institutionalized Panchayat Raj system lies 2.5 lakh villages which form the back bone of local governance and people's active participation at grass root level.

Important achievements of the same are:

1. National Integration and active people's participation: With the advent of local government people are actively involved in deciding their future. For instance, in distant villages in Jammu and Kashmir the average voter's turnout was around 80%.⁽¹¹⁾
2. Greater Participation Of women: There are over 2.5 lakh Panchayat Raj institutions in India, with over 3 million representatives in which over 1.4 million are women. India has the highest number of women representatives in the world.⁽¹²⁾

Tamil Nadu Government has even gone a step forward and made a reservation of up to 50% for the reservation of women in local bodies.

The major Lacunas' present in the working of Panchayat Raj Institutions are as follows:

1. The way the provision was made: 73rd and 74th amendment definitely did mandate the creation of PRIs. However it left upon the state to delegate the legislative powers and finances wherein the failure of the system lies. As the state governments were by and large not interested in devolving powers, responsibilities and finances to the local governments.⁽¹³⁾ The state Government did not want to devolve the subjects like health, sanitation, education to PRI's. So the PRI's who were in the best position to analyze and addresses the problem at hand were deprived of doing the same.

2. Financial Problem : The Panchayat Raj Institutions have two ways of raising finances:

A. By the way of financial devolution: this has been quite inadequate. The reason being, although the State finance Commission do recommend the state governments to devolve the resources, it is not mandatory for the state Governments to do the same. More often than not they don't Devolve the resources..

In fact, although the 14th Finance Commission had given grants of 10,000 crores worth to state government around 1600 cr were unclaimed by the states the reason being the PRI's of state did not meet the minimum requirements.

B. The second way of the PRI's to raise resources is through levying taxes, again in this front they find themselves quite inadequate as the power to tax even the subjects which are falling in their own domain has to be authorized by the state and more often than not State Governments do not do the same and hence the PRI's often find themselves starving of funds in taking on projects to achieve sustainable growth and development at grass root level. ⁽¹⁴⁾

Urban Local Government

In 2014, it was estimated that, 3.9 billion people were living in urban areas which is projected to increase to 6.3 billion by 2050. According to World Bank estimates the trend is even more pronounced in India, where according to World Bank estimates the people residing in Urban settlements in India is 55% as opposed to official estimates of 31%.⁽¹⁵⁾

Empowering the local urban bodies becomes all the more important because of the challenges that Indians living in urban areas are facing which include ⁽¹⁶⁾:

- A. Nearly one in every 6th urban people live in slums
- B. Around 41.2 million of Indian children aged from 0-6 live in urban areas, among whom more than 8.1 million children live in slums.
- C. There was a decline of births of nearly 3 million girls as opposed to births of 2 million boys during 2001 to 2011.
- D. Around 47% of children living in Indian slums are malnourished.
- E. 68% of children who live in slums are illiterate and 40% of the children work in unorganised sector.
- F. India, one of the leading economies in south Asia has 33 million children in child labour; Moreover India has also not ratified the "Minimum age convention (1973)" of International Labour Organisation.
- G. Moreover, India recently amended Child labour laws to allow children below 14 years to work in family business and entertainment industry excluding circus to maintain a balance between educational needs and socio economic needs.
- H. In urban area out of 1000 girls only 14 girls reach up to 12th standard or final year of secondary school. (in the age gap of 17 to 18 years)

I. 29% of girls in Urban India are victims of child marriage and the trend is increasing.

J. In urban India only half of the girls in the age group of 15 and 17 years attend school.

Now, when we do observe the aforesaid problems at hand it becomes ample clear that the problems which urban India is facing....is quite diverse and “one Size fits all approach” either from the ventral government or at the level of the state level is not going to be adequate to ensure that the problems at hand are effectively overcome. To overcome this there is urgent requirement of the active participation of the urban local bodies to do which they no doubt must be financially empowered as such.

Problems being faced by Urban Local Bodies

The major problems faced by urban local bodies are lack of adequate funds, skilled functionaries and disinterest of state governments in the devolution of functions to the urban local bodies.

Steps to ensure Co-Operative Federalism via fiscal federalism to ensure transforming India to a better nation

A. State Level

1. Promotion of exports: It has been quite well established that there is a positive correlation between the exports of the state and its relative prosperity. ⁽¹⁷⁾It is shown with the help of the following figure 4.

Figure 4. International Exports and States' Prosperity

Source : Survey calculations based on GST data and CSO.

Thus one of the best measures to augment the state's revenue would be Centre assisting the states in helping to take measures to increase their exports.

2. Promotion of interstate trade and imports: Interestingly it has been found out that the states who are competitive in interstate trade and imports also have export competitiveness. ⁽¹⁸⁾ Thus one of the best measures which can be taken to ensure that the states are prosperous and their revenue is complemented is to create conditions that develop their socio-economic infrastructure and complementary measures.

GST being implemented by the Government is no doubt a way forward. However on top of it Central Government developing socio economic infrastructure is not only going to add in ease of doing business, but it shall also ensure that employment opportunities are generated. The Correlation between, prosperity of states, imports and interstate trade are shown in the following figures: ⁽¹⁹⁾

Figure 5. Gross and Net Inter-State Trade of States

Source : Survey calculations based on GST data and CSO.

Figure 6. Inter-State Exports and Imports of States

Source : Survey calculations based on GST data and CSO.

3. Fiscal Devolution: A desired level of sharing of tax between centre and state must be fixed which should include both cess and surcharge. This shall definitely go a long way in augmenting the financial resources of the states.

4. Rational Tackling Of Horizontal Imbalance: During the devolution of funds when population is given weightage it disincentivises those states which are trying to bring their population under control through agreeable policies like family planning and the like. So instead of assigning weights to population alone equal weight could be assigned to both population as well as to percentage of fall in population growth rate, so as to ensure that the states which are trying to slow down their rate of population growth do not feel discouraged.

5. Special grants vs Development of socio economic infrastructure: Some of the rich states feel “cheated” ⁽¹⁹⁾ due to overuse of equity criterion while devolution of funds, The same can be addressed by giving top 3 high performing states incentives in the form giving them an infrastructural projects focussed on sustainable development which would be funded by Centre in the ratio of 55:45.

B. Strengthening Local Governing Bodies

1. Conducting Regular elections: The major problem with the Local governments particularly those present in the rural hinterland is that there is no regular elections, states tend to stall regular election despite even supreme court Judgement supporting regular elections. A legislation must be brought about to ensure that regular elections are being held.

2. To ensure grass root people’s participation effectively in elections There is a very important need to relook the verdict which was given by supreme court in Rajbala v/s State of Haryana wherein SC upheld Haryana Government’s Panchayat Raj Amendment act 2015 which keeps several prerequisites to contest elections among which the most controversial being the candidate being passed matriculation exam from a recognised board. This in Haryana wherein the rural population above the age of 20 is 90 lakh out of 1.65 crores shall be deprived from contesting. Among this 68

percent of SC women and 41 percent of SC men shall also be deprived from contesting the elections.⁽²⁰⁾

This does go against the spirit of founding fathers who gave not only voting rights but election contesting rights to every Indian who was above certain age. When the very success of Indian freedom struggle lay in masses following leaders, secluding the masses from their legitimate right does deserve to be relooked, as this judgement of supreme court does create a unfair precedent for other states to follow.

3. Properly list out subjects which would come under Local Government bodies: An effort must be made from the parliament itself to create a uniform list of some subjects which must be given to the local bodies throughout the nation, the same precedent can be applied in making another uniform list on which the local governments can levy taxes. This shall ensure that there is financial improvement in the health of local body finances.

4. Ensuring a percentage of funds are devolved regularly: Making sure that State Finance commission’s recommendation regarding devolution of funds from state to local bodies is implemented in letter and spirit. If not at least the State government must be mandated to tell to the state legislature as to why the funds were not devolved and the adequate reason thereof.

Conclusion: India which aspires to be a Global player has to ensure that all tiers of its Government machinery are well oiled and properly functioning. In this age, in past ages and in any age it has always been Economics which has driven politics, this being the case, if all the tiers of Government machinery must perform well, and if co-operative federalism must be effected and brought to action in letter and spirit, then it is necessary to have fiscal federalism. The author in this paper has made a humble attempt to start a discussion of how the fiscal federalism can be achieved so as to have co-operative federalism which can bring in required transformation in the Indian economy for better.

Annexure 1

(ii) The following abbreviations are used for the states in the paper above.

State	Abbreviation	State	Abbreviation	State	Abbreviation
Andhra Pradesh	AP	Jammu & Kashmir	JK	Punjab	PB
Assam	AS	Jharkhand	JH	Rajasthan	RJ
Bihar	BR	Karnataka	KA	Sikkim	SK
Chhattisgarh	CG	Kerala	KL	Tamil Nadu	TN
Delhi	DL	Madhya Pradesh	MP	Telangana	TS
Goa	GA	Maharashtra	MH	Tripura	TR
Gujarat	GJ	Mizoram	MZ	Uttarakhand	UK
Haryana	HR	Nagaland	NL	Uttar Pradesh	UP
Himachal Pradesh	HP	Odisha	OD	West Bengal	WB

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